

Feed additives for methane mitigation: Regulatory frameworks and scientific evidence requirements for the authorization of feed additives to mitigate ruminant methane emissions

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the regulatory and evidence requirements necessary for the authorization of anti-methanogenic feed additives (AMFA) aimed at mitigating enteric methane (CH₄) emissions from ruminants. It outlines the legislation and legal procedures in Australia, Canada, the European Union, New Zealand, South Korea, the United Kingdom, and the United States as illustrative examples, offering insights for applicants seeking authorization. Additional objectives are to highlight consequential similarities and differences in regulations and evidence requirements and offer recommendations for scientists and applicants. The pivotal role that scientific evidence plays in the evaluation and approval processes is emphasized, along with the need for applicants and researchers to understand and adhere to the specific regulations of each jurisdiction. Feed additives are regulated to ensure their safety for animals, humans, and the environment, and to verify their effectiveness for the intended use of enteric CH₄ mitigation. Regulations cover various aspects, including ingredient safety, manufacturing practices, product labeling, and the establishment of permissible limits for certain substances to ensure their safe use in animal feed. Compliance with these regulations is mandatory, and they are enforced by regulatory agencies within each jurisdiction, aiming to protect animal health, promote food safety, and prevent misleading claims and unsafe practices. The assessment processes involve evaluating scientific evidence submitted by applicants,

along with evaluations of quality control procedures, and record-keeping practices. The major difference in regulations is that each jurisdiction developed unique criteria to legally classify AMFA, making it challenging to satisfy all legal classifications with a single set of criteria for scientific evidence. However, numerous similarities and a universal reliance on the concept of intended use indicate consistency across all jurisdictions on the need for robust evidence for efficacy, safety, and product quality and documentation even if the type, size, duration, and location of the studies they require differ. Recommendations are made for both scientists and applicants, emphasizing the importance of designing, conducting, and reporting scientific evaluations transparently, using validated standards and methods, and communicating with regulatory bodies to ensure compliance with regulations and evidence requirements.

Key words: legal classification, regulatory status intended use, conditions of use, authorization, registration

INTRODUCTION

The inclusion of additives in animal feeds is regulated for various reasons. First, their use must be safe for the animals consuming them, workers manufacturing and handling them, the humans consuming food products from the animals to which they are fed, and the environment (European Commission, 2023). Second, their use must be effective for the specific purpose in feed targeted to the animal species or category for which they are marketed, which is referred to in some jurisdictions as “intended use” (US FDA, 2023). For example, applicants must present scientific evidence to the relevant authorities to obtain approval for marketing antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA) specifically aimed at enteric

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The list of standard abbreviations for JDS is available at adsa.org/jds-abbreviations-24. Nonstandard abbreviations are available in the Notes.

methane (CH₄) mitigation. Regulations also establish requirements for the labeling, and composition of AMFA and animal feeds containing them. This ensures that the labeling and packaging clearly specify the conditions for the safe and effective use of AMFA for their declared intended use. These regulations also prevent adulteration of AMFA and the animal feeds containing them. In this context, adulteration refers to the presence of any contaminants, deleterious, or unauthorized substances. Finally, regulations are meant to prevent misbranding that occurs when the labels of AMFA or animal feeds containing them either fail to include required information or provide information that is false or misleading in any way. These regulations are jurisdiction-specific and are enforced by the appropriate statutory agencies in each jurisdiction.

Science provides the foundation for the development and implementation of regulations by establishing evaluation standards and conditions of use, assessing risks, and informing policy decisions. Scientists create and validate methods for assessing the quality of AMFA and the safety and efficacy of their use. Scientists are responsible for designing, conducting, monitoring, recording, auditing, analyzing, and reporting scientific evaluations on AMFA and their conditions of use for each intended purpose. Comprehensive overviews, including methodological recommendations, on identifying (Durmic et al., 2025) and testing (Hristov et al., 2025) AMFA, modeling their effects at the animal and farm level (Dijkstra et al., 2025), understanding their mode of action (Belanche et al., 2025) and accounting their mitigation effect at the farm, regional, national, and global levels (del Prado et al., 2025) are presented elsewhere.

These evaluations apply to new uses for which applicants are seeking authorization for the first time, as well as modifications or renewals of existing uses. Scientists quantify the desired effects and assess potential risks associated with each intended use of AMFA. The risk assessments conducted by scientists are typically considered along with economic, political, and cultural interests by regulators who develop, monitor, and adjust regulations and authorization processes to mitigate or eliminate (i.e., manage) the risks associated with the uses of AMFA. For these reasons, it is critical for both the applicants and the scientists conducting the evaluations to understand the regulations and evidence requirements needed to apply successfully for authorization of AMFA in each jurisdiction they are targeting (Hegarty et al., 2021). The primary objective of this article is to outline the regulations and the evidence requirements for applicants to obtain authorization to use AMFA to mitigate enteric CH₄ emissions from ruminants in (alphabetical order) Australia, Canada, the European Union, New Zealand, South Korea, the United Kingdom, and the

United States of America as illustrative examples of relevant jurisdictions. These descriptions are intended to facilitate understanding and compliance with regulations and evidence requirements by applicants and the scientists working with them. Additional objectives are to identify consequential differences and similarities in the regulations and evidence requirements between these jurisdictions and provide recommendations for scientists and applicants. Finally, these descriptions are also of use to bodies attempting to improve harmonization among global regulatory entities.

REGULATIONS FOR ANTIMETHANOGENIC FEED ADDITIVES

Regulation refers to the set of rules established by governmental authorities to govern the manufacturing, labeling, marketing, and use of animal feed additives within their jurisdiction. Regulations for animal feed additives typically outline requirements related to ingredient safety, manufacturing practices, product labeling, packaging, and advertising. They may also establish permissible limits or maximum levels for certain substances in feed additives to ensure their safe use in animal feed. Regulations are legally binding and enforced by regulatory agencies within each jurisdiction. Compliance with these regulations is mandatory, and the applicants and users of AMFA must adhere to the specified requirements. The primary objectives of regulations are to protect animal health, promote food safety, and prevent misleading claims and unsafe practices. The following sections outline for each jurisdiction the rules or regulations that must be followed, the authority establishing those rules, and the legal classification or regulatory status that AMFA must meet for the intended use of enteric CH₄ mitigation (Figure 1).

Regulations in Australia

The regulatory framework for managing agricultural and veterinary chemicals and products in Australia is referred to as the National Registration and Accreditation Scheme (NRAS) for Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals. The NRAS is a partnership between the Commonwealth and the states and territories of Australia. The Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority (APVMA) is the independent statutory authority responsible for the regulation of the NRAS in partnership with state and territory government agencies. Among its functions, the APVMA administers the Agvet Code pursuant to the Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals Act 1994 and Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals Code Act 1994 (Australian Government, 2022). The APVMA regulates agricultural and veterinary chemicals up to and

UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

Rule: Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FD&C Act)
Authority: Food and Drug Administration (FDA) Center for Veterinary Medicine (CVM)
Regulatory Status: New animal drugs require a New Animal Drug Application (NADA).

CANADA

Rule: Feeds Act (1983), Food and Drugs Act (1985)
Authority: Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA). Health Canada Veterinary Drugs Directorate (VDD)
Regulatory Status: Gut modifiers require review and approval by the CFIA. Veterinary Drugs require review and approval by the VDD.

UNITED KINGDOM

Rule: Assimilated Regulation (EC) 1831/2003 and assimilated Commission Regulation (EC) 429/2008
Authority: Food Standards Agency (FSA) and Food Standards Scotland (FSS)
Regulatory Status: Zootechnical additives require review of a technical dossier.

SOUTH KOREA

Rule: Standards and specifications of feed, etc. (2023) pursuant to Control of Livestock and Fish Feed Act No. 17091
Authority: Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs (MAFRA) and National Institute of Animal Science (NIAS)
Regulatory Status: Methane-reducing agents require approval by the Feed Process Review Committee and registration with NIAS.

EUROPEAN UNION

Rule: Regulation (EC) 1831/2003 Regulation (EC) 767/2009
Authority: European Commission (EC)
Regulatory Status: Zootechnical additives require review of a technical dossier by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

AUSTRALIA

Rule: National Registration Scheme for Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals (NRS)
Authority: Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority (APVMA)
Regulatory Status: Veterinary chemical products require registration. Excluded nutritional or digestive (END) products are exempt from registration.

NEW ZEALAND

Rule: Agricultural Compounds and Veterinary Medicines (ACVM) Act 1997
Authority: Ministry of Primary Industries (MPI)
Regulatory Status: Inhibitors are a type of agricultural compound that require authorization by the MPI.

Figure 1. Jurisdiction-specific rules, authorities, and regulatory status (possible classifications) for the intended use of feed additives to mitigate enteric methane (CH_4) emissions from ruminants. Created by J. Tricarico and Sabrina Garay; used with permission.

including the point of retail sale, at which point thereafter regulatory responsibility is assumed by state and territories of Australia for management of use. Additives

for use in animal feed in Australia can be classified as chemical products or as excluded nutritional or digestive (END) products.

Regulations in Canada

In Canada, products added to feed with the intended purpose of enteric CH₄ reduction in livestock are classified as either veterinary drugs, reviewed and approved by Health Canada under the Food and Drugs Act (Minister of Justice, 1985), or as feeds, reviewed and approved by the Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) under the Feeds Act (Minister of Justice, 1985). This classification is primarily determined based on the mode and location of action of the product. In 2023, CFIA established the “gut modifier” legal classification through which products that act locally in the gastrointestinal tract can be considered a gut modifier and may be registered as feed (Government of Canada, 2023). According to Regulatory Guidance (RG)-1, Chapter 3- Guidance on data requirements for feed approval and registration: 3.31 Registration requirements for gut modifier products, “gut modifiers as livestock feed are products that, once fed, have a mode of action in the gastrointestinal (GI) tract of an animal. They achieve this by acting on the feed itself while in the gut or by modifying the GI environment to provide a benefit to the animal or the environment as may be linked to a nutritional effect.” For gut modifier products more generally, there are additional criteria that may distinguish if a gut modifier should be regulated as a veterinary drug or a feed as outlined in the guidance document on classification of veterinary drugs and livestock feeds. This distinction is primarily based on intended use with indications such as diagnosis, treatment, mitigation, or prevention of disease requiring classification as a veterinary drug. Reduction in CH₄ production in the rumen by AMFA is an acceptable gut modifier mode of action and gut modification claim according to guidance in “3.31 Registration requirements for gut modifier products.”

Regulations in the European Union

The European Commission (EC) is the regulatory agency that establishes regulations on feed additives in the European Union. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) evaluates the evidence for AMFA safety and efficacy for animal nutrition, human health, and the environment, and provides the EC with its opinion. The EFSA follows the rules and procedures established by the Regulation 1831/2003 (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003), which applies to all feed additives and premixtures. Fundamental to the European Union regulatory system is the distinction between feed additives and feed materials. A feed additive is defined by Regulation 1831/2003 as “substances, micro-organisms, or preparations, other than feed material and premixtures, which are intentionally added to feed or

water in order to perform, in particular, one or more of the functions mentioned in Article 5(3).” A feed additive that reduces CH₄ emissions is performing the function defined in Article 5(3)e of “favourably affecting the environmental consequences of animal production” and is classified as a zootechnical additive. Feed materials are defined in Regulation 767/2009 (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2009) as “products of vegetable or animal origin, whose principal purpose is to meet animals’ nutritional needs, in their natural state, fresh or preserved, and products derived from the industrial processing thereof.”

These definitions leave room for interpretation, an issue addressed by a Commission Recommendation in 2011 (European Commission, 2011). This recommendation recognizes that a substance cannot be both a feed additive and a feed material. It also states that the “principal purpose” of a feed material is to “meet animal’s nutritional needs,” with supply of energy, nutrients, minerals or dietary fiber and maintenance of the function of the intestinal tract considered to be the most important characteristics of a feed material. These phrases do not rule out the possibility that a feed material could have other effects, including favorable effects on the environment. The Commission Recommendation goes on to provide “criteria to be simultaneously considered in a case-by-case evaluation” to decide whether a product or substance is a feed additive or a feed material. The 3 criteria are (a) processing method (the simpler the processing, the more likely it is that the substance is a feed material), (b) safety (if a maximum inclusion level is needed to safeguard human or animal safety, the more likely it is that the substance will be regulated as a feed additive) and (c) functionality (where it is stated that a feed material “can also exert an additive function (...) but this should not be the only intended use”).

Regulations in New Zealand

The import, manufacture, sale, and use of agricultural compounds and veterinary medicines in New Zealand is regulated by 2 authorities. First, under the Hazardous Substances and New Organisms (HSNO) Act 1996 (Ministry for the Environment, 1996), any hazardous substance or new organism must be assessed and approved by the Environmental Protection Authority (EPA). A database of applications, approved substances and group standards that covers a range of products and chemicals is provided by EPA (<https://www.epa.govt.nz/database-search/>). Once approved by the EPA, agricultural compounds and veterinary medicines are regulated by the Ministry for Primary Industries (MPI) under the Agricultural Compounds and Veterinary Medicines (ACVM) Act 1997 (Ministry for Primary Industries, 1997). The MPI defines

the legal classification “inhibitors” as a substance, a mix of substances, or biological compound which mitigates adverse effects of an agricultural activity on the environment or mitigates emissions that contribute to climate change relating to plants or animals. Inhibitors can be classed as either (a) agricultural chemicals—inhibitors applied to pasture or feed crops, or crops that may be used as animal feed, or (b) veterinary medicines—inhibitors administered directly to the animal such as a vaccine, in-feed or in-water treatment, or bolus.

Regulations in South Korea

South Korea has a well-established regulatory framework for the approval and use of methane-reducing agents designed to reduce enteric CH₄ emissions in livestock. The Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs (MAFRA) establishes and enforces regulations related to overall agricultural policy and quarantine inspection of agricultural products, including livestock, dairy, and forestry products. The MAFRA Notice No. 2023–69 last amended on October 4, 2023 (Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs, 2023a), describes the “Standards and specifications for feed, etc.” In pursuant to Articles 2, 8, and 11 to 15 of the Control of Livestock and Fish Feed Act No. 17091 (Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs, 2020) and Articles 5, 11, 12, 14, and 30 of the Enforcement Rules of the same Act (Ordinance No. 627, Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs, 2023b), the purpose of this notice is to govern the scope, terminology, and guidelines for animals and feed with an emphasis on quality control and safety assurance. It also provides the criteria for feed related processes (manufacturing, usage, transportation, and storage methods), specifications for feed ingredients, ingredient registration and labeling requirements, the scope and standards of harmful substances, content and blending restrictions, and standard analysis methods.

“Feed ingredients” are defined in Article 2(2) of the Control of Livestock and Fish Feed Act as “vegetable, animal or mineral substances used either directly as feed or as raw materials for making compound feed.” Article 4(1) of the “Standards and specifications of feed, etc.” provides the catalog of *feed ingredients* specified and published by the MAFRA (MAFRA Notice No. 2023-69 Appendix 1). “Feed additive” is defined in Article 2(4) of the Control of Livestock and Fish Feed Act as “substances added to any other feed to prevent the quality of feed from deteriorating or to improve the efficacy of feed.” “Methane-reducing agents” are defined in Article 2(6) of the “Standards and specifications of feed, etc.” as “substances capable of reducing methane generated by intestinal fermentation in livestock to a certain level or higher among substances for which standards and speci-

fications have been set for single feed and supplementary feed.”

In compliance with Article 11(1) of the Control of Livestock and Fish Feed Act, Article 8(1) of the “Standards and specifications of feed, etc.” sets out the general standards and specifications for (a) feed to ensure its quality and safety (Appendix 4), (b) specific type of feed (Appendix 5), (c) specific type of feed additive (Appendix 6), and (d) methane-reducing agents (Appendix 26). Products intended to reduce enteric CH₄ emissions shall be reviewed and approved by the Feed Process Review Committee before registration with the National Institute of Animal Science (NIAS).

Regulations in the United Kingdom

Within the United Kingdom (UK), the European Union regulatory system for feed additives continues to apply to Northern Ireland after the UK left the EU, under the terms of the Northern Ireland protocol. For Great Britain (England, Scotland, and Wales), the system largely mirrors that inherited from the EU. The legal basis for the use and marketing of individual feed additives in Great Britain is assimilated Regulation 1831/2003 (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003). Risk assessment is the responsibility of the Food Standards Agency (FSA) in England and Wales, and Food Standards Scotland (FSS) in Scotland (Food Standards Scotland, 2015). Therefore, both Northern Ireland and Great Britain classify AMFA for enteric CH₄ mitigation as zootechnical additives in the same manner as in the European Union.

Regulations in the United States of America

The agency that regulates AMFA in the United States is the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). The regulation that governs AMFA is the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FD&C Act), which sets forth the requirements for the safety, quality, labeling, and approval of animal feed products (US Code of Federal Regulations, 2023). The FDA’s Center for Veterinary Medicine (CVM) is responsible for implementing and enforcing the FD&C Act for animal feed products. The CVM monitors and establishes standards for feed contaminants, approves safe and effective food additives and drugs, and manages the medicated feed and pet food programs. The CVM also cooperates with state and local authorities and industry associations, for example, the Association of Animal Feed Control Officials (AAFCO), to ensure uniform policies and standards for animal feed products across states.

Historically, the FDA classified animal foods as either feed ingredients or new animal drugs primarily based on

their intended use. Until recently, the CVM determined the regulatory status of AMFA using criteria provided by the Policy and Procedures Manual (PPM) 1240.3605 “Regulating Animal Foods with Drug Claims” (Center for Veterinary Medicine, 1998). According to this guidance nutritional and nonnutritive AMFA with the intended use (i.e., claim) of enteric CH₄ mitigation would usually have been regulated as new animal drugs by FDA. However, in May 2024, the CVM announced the withdrawal of PPM 1240.3605 (US FDA, 2024a) and their intention to review feed additives on a case-by-case basis while awaiting legislative authority from the US Congress for new legal classification categories for AMFA and other feed additives with specified intended uses that act within the gut of animals.

PROCEDURES AND EVIDENCE REQUIREMENTS FOR AUTHORIZING AMFA TO MITIGATE ENTERIC METHANE EMISSIONS

In all jurisdictions, applicants must follow specified procedures to obtain authorization and comply with regulations to lawfully market AMFA and must provide scientific evidence showing that AMFA are effective in reducing CH₄ emissions, safe for animals, food, and the environment, and of good quality. The assessments to determine whether the scientific evidence submitted in the application meets the necessary efficacy (CH₄ mitigation), safety, and quality standards are conducted by a panel of scientists appointed by the regulatory authority. Although technical recommendations on *in vitro* (Durmic et al., 2025) and *in vivo* (Hristov et al., 2025) testing of AMFA, approaches to model their effects (Dijkstra et al., 2025), describe their specific mode(s) of action (Belanche et al., 2025) and account for their mitigation impact (del Prado et al., 2025) are essential to producing robust scientific evidence, they do not replace the criteria, requirements, and guidance set by the regulatory authorities to obtain authorization to market AMFA in each jurisdiction. These assessments may also involve thorough evaluations by the regulatory authority of the manufacturing facility, including compliance with good manufacturing practices (GMP), quality control procedures, and record-keeping practices. The regulatory authority considers the recommendations from the scientific risk assessment along with other factors to approve or deny the applications. These authorizations are usually granted for a specific period and may require renewal to ensure ongoing compliance with efficacy, safety, and quality standards. Some jurisdictions, such as Australia, Canada, New Zealand, and the United States, use the term “registration” to refer to the procedure that applicants follow to obtain these premarket authoriza-

tions. The following sections outline the procedures to apply for AMFA authorization and the evaluation criteria used in different jurisdictions. These are not detailed descriptions and readers are encouraged to examine the jurisdiction-specific guidance for AMFA authorization procedures listed in Table 1.

Registration in Australia

Before an agricultural or veterinary chemical product can be legally supplied, sold, or used in Australia it must be registered by the APVMA. For a new veterinary chemical product, this is a 2-stage process. First, the active constituent must be approved before approval of new chemical products containing that active constituent. Each veterinary chemical product must have a label containing instructions on use, handling, and storage that is approved by the APVMA. Requirements for applications of new active constituent or new veterinary chemical products can be found in the “Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals Code (Application Requirements) Instrument 2014” (Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority, 2020). The APVMA provides a self-assessment tool on their website that can serve as a guide for registration of new products or active constituents (Table 1).

At present, some animal feed-based products are excluded from registration in Australia if they are fed to, and voluntarily consumed by animals, and meet 4 specified criteria. These products are referred to as END products and criteria for their classification includes the following:

- (a) **Ingredients:** The product must not contain certain ingredients such as antibiotics, and all ingredients must be on at least one of the specified lists of substances that are generally recognized as safe (the “GRAS” lists).
- (b) **Manufacturing systems:** The product must be made to one of several specified quality assurance (QA) systems.
- (c) **Labeling:** The label must contain specified information about the product.
- (d) **Claims:** The label does not include a claim that a product treats a disease, condition, or injury, unless it is specified by or in accordance with instructions of a vet and any claim is backed up by high-quality scientific evidence.

To that end, some AMFA intended for use in stock feed or as a stock feed can be marketed, sold, and used in food-producing animals without requiring registration in Australia, as reported on the APVMA website.

Table 1. Jurisdiction-specific guidance to apply for authorization of antimethanogenic feed additives (AMFA)

Jurisdiction	Title	Link
Australia	AgVet chemical regulation	https://www.apvma.gov.au/about/agvet-chemical-regulation
Australia	The record and register	https://www.apvma.gov.au/about-us/apvma-basics/what-we-regulate/record-and-register
Australia	Self-assessment tool	https://portal.apvma.gov.au/rap/dmpr-r-ag
Australia	Products excluded from registration	https://www.apvma.gov.au/registrations-and-permits/chemical-product-registration/stock-feed-pet-food-regulation
Canada	3.31 Registration requirements for gut modifier products	https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada/services/drugs-health-products/veterinary-drugs/legislation-guidelines/guidance-documents/guidance-document-classification-veterinary-drugs-livestock-feeds/document.html#a4.7.2
Canada	Guidance document on classification of veterinary drugs and livestock feeds	https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada/services/drugs-health-products/veterinary-drugs/legislation-guidelines/guidance-documents/guidance-document-classification-veterinary-drugs-livestock-feeds/document.html#a4.7.2
European Union	Feed additive applications: Regulations and guidance	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/applications/feedadditives/regulationsandguidance
European Union	Authorisation types and withdrawal	https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/animal-feed/feed-additives/authorisation-types-and-withdrawal_en
European Union	European Union Register of Feed Additives	https://ec.europa.eu/food/food-feed-portal/screen/feed-additives/search
New Zealand	ACVM registration for inhibitor applicants	https://www.mpi.govt.nz/agriculture/agricultural-compounds-vet-medicines/acvm-registration-for-inhibitor-applicants/#about
New Zealand	Inhibitor Frequently Asked Questions	https://www.mpi.govt.nz/dmsdocument/581183/direct
South Korea	Standards and specifications of feed, etc.	https://www.law.go.kr/행정규칙/사료등의기준및규격
South Korea	Feed Process Review Committee Operating Regulations	https://www.law.go.kr/행정규칙/사료공정심의위원회운영규정
United Kingdom	Apply for a regulated product authorization	https://fsa-services-eng-forms.food.gov.uk/regulated-products-application
United Kingdom	Feed additives authorisation guidance	https://www.food.gov.uk/business-guidance/feed-additives-authorisation-guidance
United Kingdom	Register of Regulated Food and Feed Products for Great Britain	https://data.food.gov.uk/regulated-products
United States of America	Regulating Animal Foods with Drug Claims	https://www.fda.gov/animal-veterinary/resources-you/how-get-new-animal-drug-approved-and-first-steps-get-started
United States of America	How to Get a New Animal Drug Approved and First Steps to Get Started	https://www.fda.gov/animal-veterinary/resources-you/how-get-new-animal-drug-approved-and-first-steps-get-started
United States of America	Part 573—Food Additives Permitted in Feed and Drinking Water of Animals	https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-21/part-573
United States of America	Official Feed Terms, Common or Usual Ingredient Names and Ingredient Definitions/A Guide to Submitting New Ingredient Definitions to AAFCO	https://apps.fass.org/FASS/survey/content/2022_OP_Chapter_6_enc.pdf#toolbar=0
Harmonized Guidance	Target Animal Safety for Pharmaceuticals	https://www.vichsec.org/en/guidelines/pharmaceuticals/pharma-safety/pharma-target-animal-safety.html
Harmonized Guidance	Good Clinical Practices	https://www.vichsec.org/en/guidelines/pharmaceuticals/pharma-efficacy/good-clinical-practice.html
Harmonized Guidance	Environmental Impact Assessment for Veterinary Medicinal Products	https://www.vichsec.org/en/guidelines/pharmaceuticals/pharma-safety/environmental-safety.html

Approval and Registration in Canada

Gut modifiers are classified and described as specialty feeds that can include one or more active gut modifier ingredients. The first step to pursue review and approval as a gut modifier is to establish the active ingredient(s) as a gut modifier by providing at least one *in vivo* or *in vitro* study that demonstrates a gut modification effect and a mode of action in the gut through original research or existing scientific literature. Feed ingredients and specialty feeds require review and approval to demonstrate that the product is safe for animals receiving it, humans consuming food products from treated animals, and users administering the product; is effective for the intended use, manufactured appropriately, labeled accurately and completely; and its impact on the environment is understood and acceptable. Guidance for approval and registration of gut modifiers is available on Section 3.31 “Registration requirements for gut modifier products” of “Chapter 3—Guidance on data requirements for feed approval and registration” within “RG-1 Regulatory Guidance: Feed Registration Procedures and Labelling Standards” in the CFIA website.

Review of animal and human safety includes, but is not limited to, potential adverse health effects, relationship to any microorganism(s) associated with adverse effects, potential for toxicity, potential for allergenicity, potential for gene transfer, potential for persistence in the gastrointestinal tract, toxicology studies, and potential exposure to humans. To demonstrate that the specialty feed has its intended effect, a minimum of 3 effectiveness studies are required. An applicant can submit studies that are published in a peer-reviewed journal or provide the raw data and statistical analyses if it is unpublished. These studies must include at least one *in vivo* study, but an applicant can also include *in vitro* studies. The guidance also states that “if an outcome is strongly correlated . . . the number of required studies may be reduced if supported by a scientific rationale.”

Authorization in the European Union

Commission Regulation 429/2008 (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2008), last amended in 2020 (European Commission, 2020), provides rules for the implementation of Regulation 1831/2003 (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003). Briefly, applicants seeking authorization must submit a technical dossier, which the Commission (responsible for risk management) will invite the EFSA (responsible for risk assessment) to evaluate. For feed additives, this falls to EFSA’s Panel on Additives and Products or Substances in Animal Feed (**FEEDAP**). At the same time, reference samples of the proposed ad-

ditive must be submitted to the Community Reference Laboratory.

Feed additives that favorably affect the environment (e.g., by reducing enteric CH₄ emissions) are a subset of additives classified as zootechnical additives. Dossiers seeking authorization of zootechnical additive application must include information on (a) the identity, characterization, conditions of use and methods of analysis of the proposed additive; (b) safety for the target species, consumers of food from the target species, those in contact with the proposed additive within the supply chain, and for the environment; and (c) efficacy.

Regulation 429/2008 states: “For additives which favorably affect the environment (e.g., reduced nitrogen or phosphorus excretion or reduced methane production, off-flavors), evidence of efficacy for the target species can be given by three short-term efficacy studies with animals showing significant beneficial effects. The studies shall take into consideration the possibility of an adaptive response to the additive.” The requirement to provide evidence of efficacy from multiple *in vivo* experiments means that building a technical dossier is generally more onerous and expensive for zootechnical additives than for most other categories. However, for zootechnical additives, authorizations are issued to “a holder of authorization” (i.e., they are brand specific). Authorizations granted for technological, sensory, and nutritional additives are not issued to specific applicants. In both cases, authorizations are valid for 10 yr, with applications for renewal required 1 yr before the expiry date of the authorization. Thus, if molecule A is authorized as a sensory additive, multiple suppliers can place it on the market, as a sensory additive. If molecule A is authorized as a zootechnical additive, only the applicant company can place it on the market. This “brand specific approval” has obvious commercial value.

Access to both scientific guidance on the design and conduct of experiments to test efficacy and administrative guidance on the preparation and submission of a dossier are provided on the EFSA website. The main aspects of the guidance to be considered in an application include the following:

- (a) The number of independent *in vivo* efficacy studies required, which depends on the number of target species/categories for which application is made:
 - i. Single animal category
 - ii. Multiple categories of the same species of food-producing animals
 - iii. Multiple species of food-producing animals (in principle, data can be extrapolated between physiologically similar species)

- (b) In vivo efficacy studies. Studies should be designed to demonstrate the efficacy of the lowest recommended level of the additive by targeting sensitive parameters usually in comparison to a negative and, optionally, a positive control group. No single design is recommended, flexibility being provided to allow for scientific discretion in the design and conduct of the studies.
- (c) Typology of studies:
 - i. Tolerance studies to provide a limited evaluation of short-term toxicity of the additive to the target animals. It is also used to establish a margin of safety, if the additive is consumed at higher doses than recommended.
 - ii. Short-term efficacy studies, including bioavailability and digestibility/balance studies.
 - iii. Long-term efficacy studies (a minimum of 3 conducted at different locations) with requirements about minimum duration (e.g., 84 d minimum for dairy cattle) and endpoints, and characteristics to be met by animals under study to apply for an animal category (e.g., age or pregnancy).

A report should be submitted for each efficacy study describing the objectives, materials and methods, results, and conclusions. The original study protocol should be included; any deviations from the original protocol should be clearly indicated and justified in the final report. The reports should include the raw data in digital format and detailed results including descriptive statistics, statistical tests, and model outcomes. It is important to note that the applicant needs to notify EFSA in advance about the start of any trial providing information about location of the study, the entity and study directors conducting the study, and the experimental design.

Registration in New Zealand

Authorization under the ACVM Act 1997 is required to import, manufacture, use or sell agricultural compounds, veterinary medicines, and, more recently, inhibitor products in New Zealand. Authorization may be in the form of registration or exemption in certain circumstances. Under the ACVM Act, applications are assessed against a risk management framework that centers around setting acceptable levels of risks and appraising risk analyses, including sufficient conditions to maintain acceptable levels of risk. The main risk areas that are assessed are in the areas of public health, trade in primary produce, animal welfare, and agricultural security. The risks are balanced against the potential for gaining benefits from the use of a compound while keeping the risks to an acceptable level. More details can be found on the risk

management under the Agricultural Compounds and Veterinary Medicines Act 1997 (Ministry for Primary Industries, 2016).

Before a law change in July 2022, inhibitors were not subject to authorization under the ACVM Act 1997. The law changed in 2022, by an order in council, declared 46 substances as agricultural compounds, subject to the ACVM Act (Ministry for Primary Industries, 2022). These agricultural compounds, therefore, require authorization if making an inhibitor claim (Ministry for Primary Industries, 2023). To register these inhibitors, the applicant will be required to provide information and research in New Zealand conditions, covering: (a) the composition of the formulation, (b) residues relating to use on food-producing crops or animals, (c) animal and plant safety, and (d) efficacy of the product. In the longer term, the New Zealand government has proposed an amendment to the ACVM Act to have all products with an inhibitor claim included in the definition of an agricultural compound, requiring everyone developing, importing, manufacturing, or selling products with an inhibitor claim to register their product with MPI (detail on the registration for inhibitor applicants is provided on their website).

Authorization and Registration in South Korea

The standards for methane-reducing agents are provided in Appendix 26 of the “Standards and specifications for feed, etc.” (Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs, 2023a). Methane-reducing agents shall be confirmed for their CH₄ reduction effects through domestic livestock experiments, following the method specified by the Director of the NIAS. To qualify as methane-reducing agents, these substances must provide proof of their effectiveness through a substantial reduction in CH₄ emissions, amounting to at least 10% compared with conventional feeding. This reduction should occur without adversely affecting the livestock health, productivity, or the safety of animal products.

Methane-reducing agents can be registered to the NIAS through the approval of the Feed Process Review Committee by evaluating the results of domestically conducted animal experiments using a respiration chamber or GreenFeed. Results for a specific species cannot be extrapolated to another; for instance, findings for beef cattle are applicable solely to that specific animal type. The assessment of methane-reducing agents must be performed by designated testing institutions recognized by the Director of NIAS, which have the capacity to conduct experiments utilizing the equipment (or experimental methods), all in the interest of ensuring objectivity. These testing institutions shall apply for accreditation to the Director of NIAS and meet the requirements set in

Appendix 3 of “Feed Process Review Committee Operating Regulations” (NIAS Directive No. 295; National Institute of Animal Science, 2023).

The scientific guidelines for conducting animal experiments for methane-reducing agents are provided in Appendix 1 and 2 and the guidelines for deliberation on recognition as *methane*-reducing agents are described in Chapter 6 of “Feed Process Review Committee Operating Regulations.” Articles 34 and 36 of the “Feed Process Review Committee Operating Regulations” provide the contents and requirements of submission materials for recognition of methane-reducing agents. The scope of the submission materials are as follows: (a) a general summary of the entire submission materials, (b) information on “manufacture of products subject to review,” (c) information on “confirmation of the product subject to review,” (d) information on “quality and safety of products subject to review,” and (e) information on “feeding effect of the product on target animal.”

In principle, animal experiments for methane-reducing agents shall meet the criteria provided in Appendix 1 and 2 of the “Feed Process Review Committee Operating Regulations,” but if not, the scientific basis for validity shall be presented. In addition, the results of accredited tests (e.g., peer-reviewed scientific papers) conducted by third parties using the same active ingredients may be presented for reference.

An applicant who intends to establish or modify a product as a methane-reducing agent shall submit the following materials (including electronic documents) to the NIAS. Applicants must provide results and raw data from animal experiments on methane-reducing agents: (a) Application Form (Form No. 2), (b) one copy of the materials specified in the scope of the submission, (c) one storage medium (CD, USB, or similar) containing the submission materials, and (d) a sample or standard of the subject matter requested by the applicant (limited to feed additives).

The submitted materials will be assessed by the Feed Process Review Committee. If the product subject to review gains approval as a methane-reducing agent from the Feed Process Review Committee, the Director of NIAS will publish the approved methane-reducing agent on their official website. Similarly, when new methane-reducing agents are registered, modified, or revoked, the Director of NIAS shall publish this information on the website, including details such as the type of feed, feed name, product name, additive standards, and the target species. In the event of new scientific findings or concerns related to approved products, reevaluation and adjustments to their efficacy or substance cancellations are possible. The Director of NIAS shall conduct inspections on testing institutions per their established requirements to maintain the accuracy and reliability of methane-

reducing agent experiments. If the Director identifies situations in which the results of these inspections could impact the accuracy and reliability of experiments, they are obligated to report to the MAFRA.

Authorization in the United Kingdom

European Union law on feed additives (Regulation 1831/2003, European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2003) continues to apply in Northern Ireland and was assimilated in Great Britain when the United Kingdom left the European Union. Application for authorizations of new AMFA, and their renewals, are processed through the online regulated product authorization service of the FSA. Technical dossiers are reviewed by the Advisory Committee on Animal Feedingstuffs (ACAF), which performs a similar function to FEEDAP in the European Union application process through EFSA. Advice on the safety and use of AMFA (i.e., risk assessment) provided by ACAF is considered by FSA/FSS to make their assessments, leading to a period of public consultation and a collective decision by relevant Ministers from the devolved nations. Guidance on the process to apply for authorization is provided in the FSA website (Table 1).

Registration in the United States of America

Until May 2024, in the United States, feed additives with indications for environmental benefits, including the intended use of enteric CH₄ mitigation in cattle, were regulated as *new animal drugs* by the United States FDA-CVM with review and approval led by the Office of New Animal Drug Evaluation (ONADE) through the New Animal Drug Application (NADA). However, FDA has been engaged in a public process of reviewing the existing policy to determine how to modernize it. The latest event in this process was the withdrawal of PPM 1240.3605 in May 2024 (US FDA, 2024a) as FDA seeks legislative authority from the US Congress for a clear regulatory pathway for AMFA. The Innovative Feed Enhancement and Economic Development Act of 2023 introduced in the Senate (S.1842; US Congress, 2023b) and the House of Representatives (H.R.6687; US Congress, 2023a) of the US Congress is a proposed law expected to provide such legislative authority to FDA. If approved, it would amend the Federal FD&C Act to create a new category of products called zootechnical animal food substances (ZAFS). The ZAFS proposed legal classification includes substances that are added to the food or drinking water of animals, act solely in gut of animals, and have the intended uses of (1) affecting the byproducts of the digestive process of animals, or (2) reducing the presence of foodborne pathogens of hu-

man health significant in animals intended to be used for food, or (3) affecting the structure or function of the body of animals, other than by providing nutritive value, by altering the animal's gastrointestinal microbiome (with some exclusions to these criteria). Consequently, various AMFA that already exist or are in development could be legally classified as ZAFS in the future. This Act would allow the products that are classified as ZAFS to be regulated as a category of feed ingredients through the Division of Animal Food Ingredients rather than as new animal drugs through ONADE. In the meantime, CVM is reviewing AMFA on a case-by-case basis. On May 28, 2024, FDA exercised its enforcement discretion after reviewing available product data and announced that while Bovaer (3-nitrooxypropanol) meets the definition of a new drug under the Federal FD&C Act, the agency did not intend to object to the marketing of Bovaer for the intended use of reducing CH₄ production in lactating dairy cows in the United States.

Because regulations are currently changing and future authorization procedures are uncertain for AMFA in the United States, the following description of the NADA process is intended to provide an illustrative example of the standards of scientific evidence expected by US regulatory authorities. Through the NADA, the applicant must demonstrate that the drug is safe for animals receiving it, humans consuming food products from treated animals, and users administering the drug, and effective (i.e., consistently has the intended effect) for a specific intended use for a specific animal species. The applicant must also establish that the characteristics of the product are consistent in its manufacturing, the labeling is accurate and complete, and the impact of the drug on the environment has been assessed. The NADA review and approval process aims to confirm the applicant's conclusion based on the submitted study data and documentation.

The NADA includes 5 major technical sections: (1) Target Animal Safety, (2) Effectiveness, (3) Human Food Safety, (4) Chemistry, Manufacturing, and Controls, and (5) Environmental Impact. The goals of the target animal safety (TAS) component are to identify potential adverse effects of the drug and establish a margin of safety for the drug. These studies are conducted with a small number of healthy animals with a signalment consistent with the intended use, and the drug is usually administered at higher doses (typically 0, 1×, 3×, and 5×, where 1× is the highest dose directed on the label) and for longer durations (typically at least 3 times the proposed duration) than the labeled dosing regimen. Sensitive populations, such as pregnant or very young animals, may require additional information on its safety.

Effectiveness studies, typically in 3 geographically distinct locations, are required to demonstrate that the

drug has its intended effect. These studies are oftentimes conducted as field studies under normal conditions and require a larger number of animals to be able to demonstrate the effect with statistical significance.

Human food safety studies examine the level of residues of the drug that may be present in food products from treated animals to ensure that they will not be harmful to people through toxicology, residue chemistry, microbial food safety, and the analytical method. The toxicology studies are intended to determine the acceptable daily intake, which is the greatest amount of the drug in a human diet that would still not be harmful. Residue chemistry examines where the drug and its metabolites go in the animal, and together with the toxicology studies, the tolerance (highest level of residue acceptable in the food products) and withdrawal period (time from when the drug was last administered to when the animal can be slaughtered or the milk can be consumed) are established. Microbial food safety is examined when a product has potential antimicrobial effects to determine the safety and potential impact of its use in food-producing animals. The analytical method describes the laboratory technique used for measuring residues in a particular animal tissue to confirm that drug residues remain below the tolerance level.

The "Chemistry, Manufacturing, and Controls" section outlines the plans for manufacturing the drug through its shelf-life to ensure that the product is high quality and safe. The environmental impact component evaluates how use of the drug could impact the environment.

A combination of laboratory and clinical studies is usually required to fulfill the requirements, and all submitted studies must be conducted using Good Laboratory Practices (GLP; US FDA, 1978) and Good Clinical Practices (GCP; US FDA, 2001), respectively, as appropriate. Pivotal studies must use the final product manufactured according to current GMP (cGMP; US FDA, 2017) guidelines. In addition to the drug label, Freedom of Information (FOI) summaries (Animal Drugs @ FDA) are publicly available and contain details about the safety and effectiveness studies conducted, submitted, and reviewed by CVM to support approval of the product (US FDA, 2024b).

DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES IN THE REGULATIONS AND EVIDENCE REQUIREMENTS ACROSS JURISDICTIONS

Thus far, this article has outlined the rules, authority, legal classification, evidence requirements and procedures necessary to apply for authorization to use AMFA in ruminants in Australia, Canada, the European Union, New Zealand, South Korea, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America. This section outlines dif-

ferences and similarities in regulations and evidence requirements across jurisdictions and identifies their major consequences.

The major difference is that each jurisdiction developed unique criteria to legally classify AMFA (i.e., determine their regulatory status). For example, in South Korea these feed additives are classified in a self-contained category as methane-reducing agents. Other jurisdictions classify them, along with feed additives that have other intended purposes, in broader categories. New Zealand classifies them as inhibitors, Canada as gut modifiers, and the European Union and the United Kingdom as zootechnical additives. The United States classified them as animal drugs until May 2024 and is currently transitioning into a new classification referred to as zootechnical animal food substances. In Australia AMFA may be classified as either veterinary chemical products or END products.

These differences in legal classification across jurisdictions have important consequences. One notable consequence is the challenge to identify a single set of global unified criteria for scientific evidence that satisfies the diverse legal classifications across all jurisdictions. For example, scientific evidence on mode of action is critically important to classify AMFA as a gut modifier in Canada, but may not be necessary in New Zealand where AMFA are classified as inhibitors. Another important consequence is related to perceptions of risk. For example, the END products option in Australia is the only AMFA category across all the jurisdictions examined that is exempt from an authorization requirement. This contrasts with requirements in all other jurisdictions, negating the need for residue and safety assessments and establishment of maximum residue limits and domestic or export withhold periods for AMFA classified as END products. The END products classification approach increases risks, as the presence of residues in an export commodity above the standards set for that commodity by an importing country could affect trade adversely. Finally, different legal classifications may function as technical and economic barriers to trade. Applicants must navigate complex guidance in most jurisdictions where they will find both differences and overlaps in evidence requirements. Regardless of the level of overlap in the evidence requirements, the costs of compliance increase each time applicants need to conduct a new study to satisfy each specific legal classification.

Based on their legal classification, each jurisdiction also developed unique procedures for obtaining authorization for intended uses of AMFA to mitigate enteric CH₄ emissions from ruminants. Although detailed procedure descriptions are beyond the scope of this article (see Table 1 for procedural guidance applicable to each jurisdiction), regulations in all jurisdictions strongly em-

phasize submitting robust evidence for efficacy, safety, and product quality even if the type, size, duration, and location of the studies they require differ. For example, South Korea applicants are required to only submit studies conducted domestically in designated testing institutions. In contrast and with some limitations, the US FDA provides guidance for including available scientific literature and studies conducted in other countries in their applications (US FDA, 2021). Therefore, the procedural differences across jurisdictions to provide evidence on efficacy, safety, and product quality for are of less significance than the consequences of having different legal classifications for AMFA.

Although regulatory frameworks and legal classifications vary, a common thread is the recognition of AMFA as essential tools in reducing enteric CH₄ emissions (Arndt et al., 2022), with each jurisdiction implementing unique but comparable procedures to evaluate and approve AMFA for this specific purpose. The following similarities across jurisdictions are important to highlight. First, all jurisdictions require comprehensive scientific evidence demonstrating that the additive is effective in reducing CH₄ emissions, is safe for the animal, does not adversely affect human health (during its manipulation in animals feeds and considering the animal food products are consumed by humans), and is not harmful to the environment. Second, the submitted evidence is assessed by scientists within regulatory bodies or appointed scientific panels. These efficacy and risk assessments, conducted by scientists, are the basis for the authorities responsible for making risk management decisions in each jurisdiction to approve or deny an application. Third, there is a universal emphasis on the need for AMFA manufacturers to ensure the quality and consistency of the additive. This includes proper labeling, documentation of ingredients, and QA procedures (Hegarty et al., 2021). Fourth, authorizations or registrations for AMFA are typically granted for a specific period, after which a renewal application may be required. This process ensures ongoing compliance with efficacy, safety, and quality standards. Finally, there is universal reliance on the concept of intended use or purpose for which the AMFA are designed, manufactured, and recommended for inclusion in targeted animal feeds.

The intended use, declared by the applicant, encompasses the effects the additive is claimed or expected to have when added to the target animal feeds, such as improving nutrition, promoting growth, enhancing feed efficiency, preventing diseases, or, critically within the scope of this article, mitigating enteric CH₄ emissions from ruminants. Intended use also considers the target animal species (e.g., beef or dairy cattle), its life stage (e.g., growing or lactating), and the specific conditions of use. The conditions of use encompass the practical as-

pects of administering AMFA to the target animal, such as active ingredient(s), dosage, mixing conditions, feeding frequency, and withdrawal period if appropriate. It is important to recognize that many substances in AMFA are novel or represent a new use case and many jurisdictions have not yet set a precedent for tolerance or usage for them in food-producing animals.

Regulatory authorities require a clear definition of the intended use as part of the application and approval process for all AMFA and complete conditions of use on all product labels. The intended use determines the scope of evaluation and the data needed for approval, including effectiveness for the claimed purpose, studies on TAS, and effects on human food safety and the environment. Therefore, intended use is a critical element in the regulatory framework for AMFA, guiding both applicants and regulators through the process of authorization and ensuring that the additive meets specified standards for its claimed purposes without adversely affecting animal health, consumer safety, or the environment. Consequently, it is inappropriate to use evidence obtained from one AMFA application to substantiate the use of another AMFA containing the same active ingredient(s) but different intended use (e.g., a different formulation).

SCIENTIFIC CONTRIBUTIONS TO AMFA REGULATION AND AUTHORIZATION

Scientists working at research institutions, the feed industry, and regulatory agencies contribute significantly to the regulation and authorization of AMFA aimed at reducing enteric CH₄ emissions. Their work spans various areas, starting with the identification and development of new, safe, and effective AMFA through dedicated research. Following discovery (Durmic et al., 2025) scientists undertake stringent testing and validation to confirm their effectiveness and safety (Hristov et al., 2025), as well as research on their mode(s) of action (Belanche et al., 2025), ensuring AMFA work as intended without adverse effects on animal health or the environment. Research to understand AMFA efficacy under different feeding conditions and their interactions with other AMFA (Hristov et al., 2025) is needed to accurately model their effects (Dijkstra et al., 2025) and account their mitigation impact through inventory and life cycle assessment methods (del Prado et al., 2025).

In addition to conducting research, scientists preferably communicate with regulatory agencies to ensure AMFA testing is conducted in ways that satisfy current safety and efficacy evidence standards. Increased collaboration on the design of experiments between scientists working in academia, industry, and regulatory agencies can streamline the collection of evidence for the approval process, preventing unnecessary replication

while ensuring only reliable additives reach the market. This collaboration is also important in addressing differences in livestock production systems through clearly researched and defined conditions of use for each application. Improving the definitions and categorization of AMFA is another valuable area for collaboration that could result in various benefits. For example, refining AMFA classifications, can help regulations evolve to reflect contemporary scientific understanding more accurately. Refined classifications can also provide more meaningful labeling and encourage uniformity across registry entries.

Education, outreach, and policy advocacy represent further avenues through which scientists make a difference. By educating stakeholders—such as farmers and feed manufacturers—about the advantages and proper application of AMFA according to specific conditions of use, scientists improve overall understanding and transparency about these substances and encourage their correct use. Additionally, advocating for supportive policies and incentives encourages the adoption of AMFA, promoting a regulatory environment that favors the deployment of safe and efficacious feed additives. These multifaceted contributions by scientists are pivotal in advancing the regulation and authorization of AMFA in a transparent manner.

Finally, scientists must recognize their contributions are limited when scientific evidence is inconclusive or lacking. For example, some jurisdictions take precautionary measures when an activity raises threats of harm to human health or the environment even if cause-and-effect relationships are not fully established scientifically (Council for Agricultural Science and Technology, 2013).

RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations for Scientists

- Design, conduct, monitor, record, audit, analyze, and report the scientific evaluations of each AMFA intended use using validated instruments, standards, and methods.
- Collaborate with regulatory bodies to design studies that comply with the regulations and satisfy evidence requirements for the evaluation process in each jurisdiction where AMFA intended uses will be evaluated for authorization.
- Share and publish the results and data of studies on AMFA intended uses in a transparent, accessible, and scientifically sound manner.
- Collaborate with regulators to improve the definitions and categories of AMFA to better reflect current science and provide more meaningful data for authorization and labeling purposes.

- Reach out to farmers, feed manufacturers, and other stakeholders about the benefits, trade-offs, and proper usage of each AMFA intended use.
- Advocate for policies that support and provide incentives for the use of authorized AMFA intended uses.

Recommendations for Applicants

- Communicate with regulatory bodies early to comply with the regulations and follow the authorization processes in each jurisdiction where AMFA are intended to be marketed.
- Provide scientifically sound data to satisfy the evidence requirements for safety, efficacy, and quality of each AMFA intended use.
- Inform farmers and other stakeholders about the benefits, trade-offs, and proper usage of authorized AMFA intended uses.

CONCLUSIONS

Regulations, evidence requirements, and procedures required for the authorization of AMFA are jurisdiction-specific and enforced by statutory agencies to protect animal health, promote food safety, and prevent misleading claims. All jurisdictions authorize AMFA based on intended use or purpose for which they are designed, manufactured, and recommended for inclusion in targeted animal feeds. In all jurisdictions, the authorization of AMFA is contingent upon a scientific evaluation demonstrating that the additive's intended use does not pose harmful effects and is effective in reducing emissions. Scientists conduct efficacy and risk assessments that are used by the responsible authorities in each jurisdiction to make the risk management decisions to approve or deny applications for each AMFA intended use. Applicants and scientists involved in evaluating AMFA must understand and follow the jurisdiction-specific regulations and evidence requirements.

The major difference in regulations is that each jurisdiction has developed unique criteria to legally classify AMFA. The consequential implications are the challenge to identify a single set of criteria for scientific evidence that satisfies all legal classifications, varying perceptions of risk, increased costs of compliance as targeted jurisdictions increase, and the existence of technical and economic barriers to trade across jurisdictions. In contrast, numerous similarities indicate consistency across all jurisdictions on the need for robust evidence for efficacy, safety, and product quality and documentation, even if the type, size, duration, and location of the studies they require differ. The resultant outcome is that regula-

tory authorities across different jurisdictions implement unique but comparable procedures for evaluating and approving AMFA, with a universal emphasis on comprehensive scientific evidence to support the claims about the additives.

The intended use declared by the applicant has a crucial role in the process of authorization and ensuring that specified standards for its claimed purposes are met without adversely affecting animal health, consumer safety, or the environment. The intended use also requires that the practical aspects of administering AMFA to the target animals (conditions of use) are communicated clearly and completely. Therefore, it is inappropriate to use evidence obtained from one AMFA intended use to substantiate another AMFA sharing the same active ingredient(s) if their intended uses differ, for example, due to different formulations, dosages, or applications. Regulatory agencies emphasize the importance of evaluating each AMFA independently, considering its specific intended use and associated risks.

Scientists make essential contributions to the development of regulatory frameworks and play a vital role in generating evidence to ensure that AMFA meet rigorous standards for safety, efficacy, and quality, thereby facilitating their responsible use in livestock production systems. By educating stakeholders, such as farmers and feed manufacturers, about the advantages and proper conditions of use of each AMFA scientists can encourage correct use of AMFA and improve overall understanding and transparency on them. In addition, by collaborating on refining legal classifications for AMFA, scientists can help regulations evolve to more accurately reflect contemporary scientific understanding and provide more meaningful labeling while encouraging uniformity across registry entries. Recommendations to follow good scientific practices is a good reminder for scientists and critical for applicants and dairy sector stakeholders that use the resulting science to substantiate their decisions to use AMFA. Finally, it is recommended that applicants and scientists consult with the appropriate authorities in each jurisdiction before designing and conducting research studies intended for authorization of all AMFA intended uses.

NOTES

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Nonstandard abbreviations used: ACVM = agricultural compounds and veterinary medicines; ACAF = Advisory Committee on Animal Feedingstuffs; AMFA = antimethanogenic feed additives; APVMA = Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority; CFIA = Canadian Food Inspection Agency; CVM = Center for Veterinary Medicine; EPA = Environmental Protection Authority; EFSA = European Food Safety Authority; END = excluded nutritional or digestive; FAP = Food Additive Petition; FDA = Food and Drug Administration; FSA = Food Standards Agency; FSS = Food Standards Scotland; GRAS = generally recognized as safe; GMP = good manufacturing practices; HSNO = hazardous substances and new organisms; MAFRA = Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs; MPI = Ministry for Primary Industries; NIAS = National Institute of Animal Science; NRS = National Registration Scheme; NADA = New Animal Drug Application; ONADE = Office of New Animal Drug Evaluation; PPM = Policy & Procedures Manual; QA = quality assurance; ZAFS = zootechnical animal food substances.

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